

Quan Âm Tu Viện

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Entry tags: Tibetan Buddhism, Temple, Vietnam, Vietnamese Religions, Religious Group, Southeast Asian Religions, Religious Place, Mahayana-Vajrayana Hybrid, Vajrayana

Quan Âm Tu Viện is located in the residential area of Phú Nhuận district in Hồ Chí Minh City. Dating back to the 1960s, the monastery land was originally a water-logged islet accessible only by boat. Now bridges cross the Nhiêu Lộc - Thị Nghè Canal, which makes it more convenient to access the monastery. As the name suggests, it is primarily dedicated to the worship of the compassion Bodhisattva, Avalokitesvara, called Quan Âm in Vietnamese. In contrast to Vajrayana where Avalokitesvara is depicted in male form, he is represented as female in Vietnamese Mahayana. Quan Âm Tu Viện epitomizes syncretism between Vietnamese Mahayana and Vajrayana aesthetics, rituals and teachings. Prior to 2010, the monastery was purely Mahayana with only one main hall located on the second floor of the main structure. After becoming allied with Gyalwang Drukpa, the reincarnate spiritual leader of the Drukpa lineage, founded by Naropa over 1,000 years ago, the temple began hybridizing, turning the lecture hall on the ground floor into a second main hall dedicated to Vajrayana deities. The monastery is known for its connection with the Drukpa lineage of Tibetan Buddhism, its prominent abbot (who is allied with the Vietnam Buddhist Sangha, or VBS) and its notable followers, which include top entrepreneurs, government officials and cultural influencers. There are two groups that share occupancy: the Mahayana Great Compassion group and an unnamed Vajrayana group that is composed of primarily young and cosmopolitan followers and meets whenever Tibetans are in residence. Gyalwang Drukpa and his sangha visit the temple once a year around Tết Nguyên Đán (Vietnamese Lunar New Year) and attract thousands of people and national media coverage. He first visited Vietnam in 2007 and has been coming back regularly ever since, marking his 12th time returning in 2023. The Drukpa sangha is hosted in Great Mandala Stupa in the north and Quan Âm Tu Viện in the south. Quan Âm Tu Viện, in association with its sister temple in the nearby province of Bình Phước, which is a purely Mahayana temple, often organize short-term retreats and teachings for lay people, especially for family and young children. Quan Âm Tu Viện is also known for running a traditional Vietnamese medical clinic called Tuệ Tĩnh Đường, which provides free healthcare services to disadvantaged people. In Hồ Chí Minh City, Quan Âm Tu Viện is commonly known for being one of the few Vajrayana temples, besides the nearby Chùa Lâm Huệ.

Date Range: 1960 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Phú Nhuận district, Hồ Chí Minh City

Region tags: Asia, Vietnam, Southeast Asia

Quan Âm Tu Viện is located on Trường Sa street, ward 2, Phú Nhuận district, Hồ Chí Minh City.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gyalwang Drukpa. 2015. Nghi quỹ tu trì giản lược Đức bản tôn Hoàng Tài Bảo Thiên [Abridged sadhana of Zambala]. Hanoi: NXB Tôn giáo
- Source 2: Drukpa Vietnam. 2015. Đại Bảo Tháp Mandala Tây Thiên [Great Mandala Stupa]. Hanoi: NXB Tôn giáo.
- Source 3: Kyabje Khamtrul Rinpoche and Jigme Pema Nyinjadh. 2011. Bản tôn chân ngôn trí tuệ Kim Cương Thừa [Vajrayana Mantra of Wisdom]. Hanoi: NXB Tôn giáo.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SEj2utSeyPk>
- Source 1 Description: 11 minute video showing the temple architecture and religious objects in the temple property.
- Source 2 URL: <https://quanamtuvien.vn/>
- Source 2 Description: Official website of the temple
- Source 3 URL: A 2023 Drukpa empowerment held at the temple.
- Source 3 Description: <https://phatgiao.org.vn/le-quan-danh-phat-danh-ton-thang-namgyelma-tai-quan-am-tu-vien-duoi-su-chu-tri-duc-drukpa-thuksey-rinpoche-d71937.html>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

DRAFT

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: Back in the 1960s, the monastery was located on an islet across from the city center that was only accessible by boat. In the present, bridges are built for more convenient commute across the Nhiêu Lộc - Thị Nghè Canal.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Notes: Phú Nhuận is an urban district of Ho Chi Minh City with the population of over 160,000 people (according to the 2019 census).

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery is situated within tall walls that separate it from the surrounding houses.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The monastery is located right at the center of an urban residential area in Phú Nhuận district.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: Residential houses are adjacent to the temple.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: For a video overview of the monastery, see here: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4Dqogp_3e0E

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Several features including statues, buildings, stupas.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The temple has gone through multiple renovations with the most recent major change being the transformation of the lecture hall on the ground floor into a Vajrayana main hall post 2010s.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The temple has gone through multiple renovations with the most recent major change being the transformation of the lecture hall on the ground floor into a Vajrayana main hall post 2010s.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Quan Âm Tu Viện is part of Tổ đình Vĩnh Nghiêm, a major Mahayana school in Vietnam.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: Besides religious worship, the monastery has a small clinic attached to side that offers traditional Vietnamese healing for poor and disadvantaged population.

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: Communal uses include chanting and empowerments. Individual uses are common as well.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Post 2010, after the first visit of Gyalwang Drukpa and his sangha to Quan Âm Tu Viện, the temple renovated the ground floor, which was an empty gathering hall, to a Vajrayana main hall.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: 2000 and 2005

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: A panoply of Vajrayana and Mahayana deities, such as Avalokiteshvara or Quan Âm, Matriya or Phật Di Lặc, Zambala or Hoàng Thần Tài, and many more.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery hosts both Vajrayana and Mahayana events for the commemoration of ancestors with prayers for peace (cầu an) and devotional prayers (cầu siêu).

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Notes: Even though not officially commemorate a specific group, but Quan Âm Tu Viện is known for its dedication to Drukpa as the only Vajrayana lineage that is invited to host empowerments and rituals at the temple.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery has the main structure in the center with two main halls, on the ground floor is the hall dedicated to Vajrayana panoply and the second floor is worshipped the Vietnamese Mahayana's Three Jewels. On the sides are residence for the nuns with a kitchen and an administrative office. On the courtyard, there is a stupa for the previous abbot, Thích Nữ Huệ Giác, who passed away in August 2022. The temple has the main Avalokiteshrava statue in the courtyard against a man-made rock backdrop.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The main temple hall, where on the ground floor is dedicated to Vajrayana worship and the upper floor is for Mahayana practices, is the focal point of religious action.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– No

Notes: The temple and other buildings (residence, kitchen) are made from cement, although doors in the main hall are made of wood.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: concrete and brick

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery has rich decorations in which many are typical of Mahayana temples, such as murals, carvings, rockeries, etc. What stands out is the fusion with Vajrayana decorations, such as thangkas and statues.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Especially Tibetan scroll paintings (thangkas).

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: In the Vajrayana section, the main deity is Avalokiteshvara, the compassion bodhisattva. Various deities float in Pure Land behind it. To the left is a prominent statue of Zambala with a donation box attached. There are several thangkas with various deities. Upstairs is a statue of Siddhartha Buddha. Outside is a statue of Quan Âm. Other deities are Maitreya, dharma protectors, and Medicine Buddha.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: A prominent statue of the Buddha with his finger raised (in an act of protection) has a mural behind with human attendants.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Quan Âm statue is depicted riding a dragon.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: Some abstract and decorative patterns typical of Tibetan Buddhist temples (for example, mandala thangkas).

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Notes: For example, on the wall surrounding the Mahayana main hall there are narrative murals on the life of Buddha.

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Narratives of the life of the Buddha.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Notes: While the iconography is all relatively standard for Buddhism, what is unique about this temple is the juxtaposition and hybridity of the iconography. It typifies a small but growing trend for Mahayana temples to have strong Vajrayana iconographic elements, mixed in together. It is the recombination that is notable and constitutes a "distinct feature".

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: Tibetan statues are made in a stylized fashion normal for the region.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Various deities and dharma protectors take human form.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: In the Vajrayana part of the temple, bodhisattvas float on clouds in the heavenly realm of Pure Land.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: These includes vajra, swastika, and mudras among many other things.

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Narrative murals of the life of Buddha.

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Lotus decorations floating in the nearby river.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Even though not a place for burial, the cremated remains of the previous abbot, Thích Nữ Như Giác, are kept inside a stupa on temple ground.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: As it is common in Vietnamese Mahayana temples, there is a columbarium chamber at Quan Âm Tu Viện that keeps the urns and photos of the deceased for worshipping purposes.

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: There is no supreme god within the panoply of Tibetan Buddhist deities.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits are believed to take sanctuary inside the temple, especially those that have passed away within 49 days and their cremated remains and/or photos are stored there.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Notes: A straightforward example of this are tulkus or reincarnated lamas.

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Drukpa tulkus and rinpoches, as examples of mixed human-divine beings, frequent the temple and communicate with followers both in directly and through supernatural means.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– I don't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– No

↳ Offerings of food:

–Yes [specify]: tsok - an important Vajrayana practice of offering food and drink.

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– I don't know

↳ Daily life objects:

–Yes [specify]: Food, clothing and daily essentials

↳ Other:
–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: This temple is notable for being popular among LGBTQ+ followers -- although the temple does not openly support queer sexuality.

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Rituals are typically called empowerments and are the hallmark of Vajrayana practices at the temple. We attended a few, including Zambala -- the most popular because they promote wealth, which appeals to the demographic of business people and celebrities of Quan Âm Tu Viện's followers.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The largest ritual is hosted by Gyalwang Drukpa and his sangha which can attract up to a thousand people.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Multiple small Mahayana and Vajrayana rituals are done throughout the year at Quan Âm Tu Viện. In addition to rituals, they have started to organize talkshow. The first one is hosted by a prominent follower and Tiktok influencer, Thy Huyfnh, and a wealthy business man, Minh Nhựt on September 30th, 2023.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: 1000

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: annually

Notes: The large-scale rituals that welcome the Drukpa sangha are organized annually, typically around the time of Tet (Vietnamese Lunar New Year). However, during the year, there are multiple Drukpa lamas coming to Quan Âm Tu Viện that attract hundreds of participants.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The abbot, Thích Nữ Huệ Đức, is the student of the High Venerable Thích Viên Thành - the 11th Head of Tổ đình Hương Tích or Chùa Hương, and Gyalwang Drukpa of Tibetan Buddhism, maintains orthodoxy and orthopraxy checks on Mahayana and Tibetan rituals at the temple.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The abbot, Thích Nữ Huệ Đức, is the student of the High Venerable Thích Viên Thành - the 11th Head of Tổ đình Hương Tích or Chùa Hương, and Gyalwang Drukpa of Tibetan

Buddhism, maintains orthodoxy and orthopraxy checks on Mahayana and Tibetan rituals at the temple.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: Donations come in different forms: dropping cash inside donation boxes or wire transfer to the temple's bank account, food and flower offerings.

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the Vajrayana statues in the main hall was donated to the temple by its prominent followers. in return, these followers receive VIP treatment that includes seating in the main hall and be in presence of Tibetan lamas when they come.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: Repairs and cleaning are often done by resident nuns, with the help of volunteers, especially after events.

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Notes: Temple cleaning and sweeping are done by in-residence nuns.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: There are no formal pilgrimages that begin or end at the temple. However, Drukpa followers shadow the sangha around the country when they come, and one of the major stops is Quan Âm Tu Viện. This does not constitute formal pilgrimage practices endorsed by temple leadership.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Notes: Feasting is typical of many Mahayana temples in Vietnam, where after a ritual event there is a free meal. The food is always vegetarian.

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– Yes

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– No

Notes: The temple provides free lunch for religious specialists and participants. Food is prepackaged and distributed to participants to eat at their sitting.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: For Mahayana, festival is organized during the month of Vesak and includes Buddha showering ceremony and sutra recitation.

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: annually

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:
– Yes

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:
– Yes

Notes: Mostly decorations in the Vesak month.

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):
– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
– number: 1000

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
– Yes

Notes: Lunch and water are always provided to all participants.

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
– Elites
– Non-elites
– Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– No

↳ Divination through human communication:

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Divination is highly personalized and personal and variable.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to spirit healing, there is a free Sino-Vietnamese medical clinic associated with the temple.

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: There are approximately 20 nuns living fulltime at the temple, and another 10 nuns residing in Quan Âm Tu Viện's associate temple called Thiền viện Trúc Lâm Bình Phước.

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: Tibetan lamas occasionally visit the temple and stay for a short time to host ceremonies and empowerments.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Quan Âm Tu Viện is a nunnery with all religious specialists are female.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Notes: It is common for nuns to live in a temple for life. However, they might receive reallocation order to serve as abbots of other temples in the future.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The temple has dedicated infrastructure for permanent residence.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The temple offers both short and long-term retreat for religious specialists and lay people.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: As the temple is an official member of the Vietnam Buddhist Sangha (VBS), it is under the supervision and management of VBS Phú Nhuận.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Notes: Even though the temple is under the administrative monitoring of the Vietnam Buddhist Sangha (VBS), as any other officially recognized Buddhist sites are in Vietnam, there is no formal bureaucracy at the temple. The abbot, Thích Nữ Huệ Đức, is a member of the administrative board of the local district VBS.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: According to the Vietnam Buddhist Sangha (VBS) Charter (revised in 2022), temples have legal rights to land and donation usage (Chapter VIII, Article 55).

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Notes: Primary income of the temple comes from donations. The new Circular No. 04/2023/TT-BTC on Guidelines for Management, Collection and Use of funding for organization of festivals and religious donations or grants for relic sites and festivities issued on January 19, 2023 regulates donations of all religious sites in Vietnam. According to the circular, religious institutions are required to open a deposit account at either the State Treasury or a commercial bank to keep record of the money donated through wire transfers. Cash donations are required to be counted weekly and deposited to the opened bank account. Each religious institution is expected to produce annual financial reports, but not required to submit to any state agencies. Individual temples and pagodas are still responsible for their own donation collection, management and usage.

Does this place lease out land:

– No

Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: The temple gives out free lunch and water for all attendants during empowerments hosted by Drukpa lamas (Gyalwang Drukpa, Drukpa Thuksey, Gylwa Dokhampa, etc.)

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

Notes: The temple is a place for gathering in festive occasions, such as the Mid-Autumn festival, for children and families.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: It is located in the residential area of Phú Nhuận district and accessible by road.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The temple runs a traditional (Sino-Vietnamese) medicine clinic called Tuệ Tĩnh Đường that provides free healthcare services to poor people.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: The temple has an office that handles administrative works. Non-religious records and documents are stored here. In addition, according to the new Circular No. 04/2023/TT-BTC on Guidelines for Management, Collection and Use of funding for organization of festivals and religious

donations or grants for relic sites and festivities issued on January 19, 2023, religious institutions are expected to produce annual financial reports, but not required to submit to any state agencies. These records are stored in the office within the temple premise.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No